

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D2.3: First data status and analytics

WP2: New insight of high-resolution coastal observations

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1. Executive Summary

Project context

The **FOCCUS project** (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to enhance coastal ocean observation and forecasting for Copernicus users by designing and implementing a range of high-resolution data products. **Work Package 2 (WP2)** focuses on improving pan-European **innovative coastal ocean observations** in response to society and EU policy needs in the context of climate change.

Scope of subtask 2.3.2 and of this deliverable

Within this task, the objective is to display the existing and available coastal and river data.

There is already a lot of coastal in-situ data within the Copernicus Marine Service, as part of the in-situ products of the catalogue, but as yet there are no specific analyses of these data products. The objective of this deliverable is to highlight and detail the in-situ coastal data available within the Copernicus Marine Service (this deliverable) in order to verify with the providers and the users that the information is correct and sufficient to display the data owner and data flow. Where possible, corrections will be made by the In Situ TAC partners (the Copernicus Marine consortium in charge of the in situ products in the Copernicus Marine Service) or will be listed with an updated plan (final deliverable, update of the present one).

The Copernicus in situ data are mainly from direct in situ measurements with some homogenisation and quality control according to the FAIR principles. The resulting generic product has been used for many purposes for numerical modelling and assimilation, for short term (real time) and long term (climate) studies and for various societal applications including EU policy needs. Thanks to this task, the coastal part of this product will be improved, no doubt by adding some new data, but above all by correcting and completing the information associated with the existing data, with the help of data suppliers and managers.

Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable (D2.3) provides an initial inventory of coastal and river data status and statistics.

The **coastal data** inventory includes the 10 main in situ platform types available in the Copernicus Marine Service. The inventory is made by platform types and provides various information and statistics to give an overview of the data available (e.g. institution owner, country owner, geographical position, parameters, measurement period) in the Copernicus Marine Service for the provider and the data manager (including the FOCCUS partners) to have the opportunity to complete or correct the information provided.

The **river data** inventory includes major rivers across European countries and some American countries. Data considered are at the river mouth, defined at the point where there is no more salty (no tide influence) waters, and must include the water flux. These first status and statistics will hopefully allow for improving data management homogenisation that will be proposed by FOCCUS partners, EMODnet physics and the Copernicus Marine Service.

2. Coastal Data

Within the Copernicus Marine Service, the in situ products of the catalogue provide open sea and coastal data. For the FOCCUS project as the attention is on coastal data, it is an opportunity to identify the marine in situ coastal data that are integrated within Copernicus products, and to enhance its visibility and traceability (from the source and the data owner).

Note this inventory is done on the Copernicus Marine Service, which contains a huge amount of data all over the world. Variables considered are for the physics: temperature, salinity, sea level, currents, waves and for the biogeochemistry: chlorophyll concentration, dissolved oxygen concentration, nutrient (nitrate, phosphate, silicate) concentration and variables linked with the carbonate system (e.g. pH, alkalinity, pCO₂). This data mainly comes from measurements taken by autonomous platforms, with the exception of bottle data, for which physical and biogeochemical data are measured in the laboratory during or after the research campaign.

Coastal data is defined following the CoastPredict Programme approach as data above a depth of 400m and less than 200km from the coast. Only European countries (mainlands) are considered. For mobile platforms, the first position (longitude and latitude) in the file defines whether the platform is coastal or not.

The Copernicus Marine Service is an open and free service and therefore the in situ data comes from open and free data sources (CC-BY licence or equivalent). No other data: not open, paying is considered.

EMODnet Physics harvests three times per day the in situ Copernicus Marine products and also contains data with little metadata, very short periods, and with other variables (e.g. sound, river). Thanks to this deliverable and a close cooperation between the in situ component of the Copernicus Marine Service (the In Situ TAC) and EMODnet Physics, improvements proposed for in situ Copernicus Marine products will benefit the EMODnet Physics database.

JERICO, as an integrated pan-European multidisciplinary and multi-platform research infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes, has already identified and worked on many coastal data owned in different European countries. The data are distributed through national and European databases and aggregators and need to be clearly identified. In particular, this identification must be made by the Copernicus Marine Service and it is one of the themes of this deliverable to take stock of this issue.

The deliverable will detail the in situ coastal dataset considering the 10 main platform types available in the Copernicus Marine Service. There are the fixed platforms:

- moorings,
- tide gauges,
- HF radar,

and the mobile ones:

- research vessels with CDT,
- XBT (temperature sensor),
- bottles,
- gliders,
- drifting buoys,

- profiling floats,
- ferryboxes.

We look at 10479 European coastal platforms available in the Copernicus Marine Service, which counts more than 81500 platforms (altogether around the global ocean) beginning in 2025 when the download of the data was made for this study. These coastal European data that represent 13% out of all Copernicus Marine platforms, from which this study has been done, are available through Seanoe (<https://doi.org/10.17882/107355>).

The geographical coverage extends from West to East, from the Azores to the tip of the Black Sea, and from South to North, from the Canary Islands to Iceland. However, it was identified during the later stages of the review process that the current bound box selection does not encompass certain high-latitude stations in the northernmost part of Norway, as they fall outside the predefined spatial extent. This will be adjusted and properly addressed in the final deliverable (D3.3.¹ to be submitted in December 2027, led by +ATLANTIC), to ensure a more comprehensive inclusion of relevant data sources.

Fixed buoys, mooring time series, fixed observations (MO)

Fixed buoys, mooring time series, and fixed observations include a wide range of observations at specific locations. These platforms can be moored buoys dedicated to measuring different parameters such as temperature, salinity, wave parameters, currents and biogeochemical parameters such as chlorophyll-a or nutrient concentration. Measurements can be taken at the surface, within the water column, or from bottom stations. These measurements can be associated with historical and long time series. For example, sea temperature observations available in the Copernicus Marine Service from stations in Sweden were collected from 1883 onwards.

Inventory and status

858 coastal platforms are available in the Copernicus Marine Service.

¹ Deliverable D3.3 Final Data Status and Analytics, is a report from WP3 that is to be submitted at the end of the project in M36, and led by partner +Atlantic. It will contain final in situ coastal and river data status and statistics. This deliverable will be part of *Subtask 3.3.1 Improving quality and processing of coastal observations with Artificial intelligence*, and *Subtask 3.3.2 Improving traceability and tracking of in situ coastal and river data*. This includes a final assessment of the improvement in in situ coastal and river data product identification, traceability and tracking, and final establishment of statistics mainly on the number of coastal and river data out of the total number of data and its evolution with time. For river data, final statistics and metrics will provide the number of countries and stations in EMODnet.

Figure 1. Moored coastal platforms in Copernicus Marine Service

Analysis

When all moored platforms are considered, a significant proportion of platforms is associated with historical data, as 49% (421 platforms) have not sent any data since the beginning of 2024. Based on data collected since the beginning of 2025, it can be stated that 378 platforms (44%) in the Copernicus Marine Service are active.

113 institutions distributed across 24 countries (Figure 2) were involved in building such a dataset. The institution and the institution country of 9 fixed buoys are not documented.

6% (56 platforms) refer to JERICO and 84% (720 platforms) are not associated with any project.

Figure 2. Percentage of moorings per country

When we consider the observed parameters, we can identify 4 main groups of moorings:

- platforms dedicated primarily to **physical** parameters (temperature, salinity, currents),
- platforms dedicated primarily to **waves** measurements,
- platforms dedicated primarily to **biogeochemical** parameters.

Of the 858 platforms, 626 (73%) measure sea temperature (Figure 3), but only 208 of the coastal platforms (24%) include both temperature and salinity measurements. Coastal platforms measuring currents are less common, with only 174 platforms (20% of fixed platforms) doing so. In coastal environments, water turbidity is also a key parameter. Within the Copernicus Marine Service, 68 platforms (8%) provide turbidity data (even if this is not an essential parameter of the in situ Copernicus component yet).

Figure 3. Moored coastal physical platforms measuring at least temperature

Different platform designs are used for the waves and they do not measure the same parameters. However, if we consider one of the most common parameters (VHM0 - Spectral significant wave height - H_{m0} and VGHS - Generic Significant Wave Height - H_s), we can identify 486 platforms (57%) that are able to collect wave parameters (Figure 4). Considering these buoys, 69% (335 platforms) also measure sea temperature.

Figure 4. Moored coastal physical platforms measuring at least spectral significant wave height

For platforms mainly dedicated to biogeochemical parameters, different variables can be considered.

When analyzing the database, we first consider the fixed buoys measuring chlorophyll concentration (here we consider the total chlorophyll concentration or Chlorophyll-a concentration or Fluorescence). There are 30 platforms (3% of fixed platforms) measuring this.

Concerning the oxygen concentration, 108 platforms (13%) are identified as measuring this.

Ship/XBT platforms (XB)

An Expendable Bathythermograph (XBT) is a probe used to measure temperature throughout the water column. It is launched from a research vessel during a marine campaign or from any other ship of opportunity.

Inventory and status

Figure 5. coastal XBT platforms in the Copernicus Marine Service. Each dot corresponds to the first launch of a XBT (or MBT) from a different ship.

There are 597 XBT platforms within the Copernicus Marine Service “initiated” in the coastal European seas. This means there are 597 different ships launching XBT (and a few MBT Mechanical Bathythermograph) with a first launch in the coastal area. Indeed XBT profiles (one longitude, one latitude and several depths) measured from a same ship are gathered in one only file, which then contains all XBT profiles along the ship route over months or years. The period covered depends on the duration and the number of sea campaigns (note there are periods with no data as there are no campaigns nor measurements).

Analysis

Of these 597 XBT platforms, 109 (18%) have an identified institution and 488 (82%) do not. The 109 platforms identified belong in fact to 21 different institutions.

Of these same XBT platforms, 158 (27%) have an identified country and 439 (73%) do not. Of the 158 XBT platforms with identified countries, we find 23 different countries with the following distribution in XBT with great disparity:

- Bahamas, Canada, Israel, Japan, Liberia, Panama, Portugal, Singapore, South Africa, Turkey: 1

- Antigua, Netherlands, Russia: 2
- Croatia, Cyprus, Spain: 3
- Greece: 4
- Sweden: 6
- Germany: 7
- UK: 8
- Italy: 12
- USA: 14
- France : 82

Indeed, half of the ship/XBT platforms identified are done by France.

55% (326) of platforms are identified by a WMO platform code and 8% (48) have an ICES code. All ship/XBT platforms have a platform code and 95% (565) have a platform name. 14% (86) are also referenced by a project code, of which there are 2: Fr-OOS (French Ocean Observing System) and GOSUD (Global Ocean Surface Underway Data). As expected, there is no reference to JERICO, which does not include this type of platform.

Of course, all the platforms measure temperature, although some of them (3%, 19 platforms) also measure salinity.

The oldest measurement dates from 1941 (unknown institution and country) and 6 ship/XBT platforms active in 2024 (operational) were in Copernicus in January 2025 when the files were downloaded for this study.

Ship/CTD platforms (CT)

A Conductivity Temperature and Depth (CTD) sensor allows mainly the measurement of the temperature, salinity, and pressure throughout the water column (additional parameters can also be measured). As with the XBT, it is operated from a research vessel during a marine campaign or from any other ship of opportunity. But unlike an XBT, the CTD is recovered after each measurement.

Inventory and status

Figure 6. Coastal CTD platforms in the Copernicus Marine Service.

There are 2063 ship/CTD platforms within the Copernicus Marine Service with a first measurement made in the EU coastal area. CTD platforms are mainly launched from a ship (research vessel or ship of opportunity), however some CTD platforms are also fixed in space (which probably correspond to a ship station which can be repeated years after years). In each case, the data file contains the whole time series, i.e. profiles along the route of the ship from one marine campaign to another one in the first case and 1 time series of a unique profile at a specific place which can contain gaps if, for example, measurements are made only at some period of the year in the second case. For a few CTDs, there is only one observation (one profile measured at only one time).

Analysis

Out of these 2063 platforms, 786 (38%) have an identified institution and altogether there are 32 different institutions.

1198 platforms (58%) have an identified country while 865 (42%) do not have the information. The ship/CTD platforms belong to 28 different countries. The distribution of the ship/CTD platforms by country does not make much sense as its definition is not unique.

All platforms that host the CDT probes are identified by a platform code and 75% of them have a platform name, while 13% have a WMO code and 9 of them have an ICES one. Projects or programmes identified are Fr-OOS and GOSUD but for only 46 platforms (2%). CTD platforms are not part of JERICO and therefore not identified as such.

Nearly all (actually 2053 out of 2063) CTDs measure temperature and most of them (1961, 95%) measure salinity as well. In addition, nearly half of them (49%) also measure oxygen. Few other biogeochemical parameters are measured: chlorophyll-a concentration (2%), carbonate system (2%) and nutrient concentrations (nitrate, phosphate and silicate) (1%) and two platforms provide the current.

The measurements are profiles in the water column, from surface or subsurface down to a maximum of 5000 m depth.

CTD measurements are among the first data to have been collected at sea. The first measurement in the coastal area found in the Copernicus Marine Service dates from 1884 and was done by Ukraine (Pomona ship). 125 CTD (6%) were active in 2024 or at the very beginning of 2025 before the files were downloaded from Copernicus.

Ship/bottle platforms (BO)

A bottle allows for making physical and biogeochemical measurements in the water column. The vertical profiles are made for the surface or subsurface to a maximum depth of 1000 m. Water samples are taken from a ship during a research campaign and measurements are done afterwards in the laboratory. The bottle is the only non-automated platform type that is considered within the Copernicus Marine Service.

Inventory and status

Figure 7. Coastal bottle platforms in the Copernicus Marine Service.

There are 2585 bottle platforms within the Copernicus Marine Service in the coastal European area. Measurements are made either from a research vessel during a campaign or at specific points regularly in time by a dedicated ship. It also happens (especially from old data) that there is only one observation (one date and one position). Data acquired during research campaigns by one vessel are gathered together in only one file (i.e. there is one file by research vessel, as for the XBT). However, ship/bottle platform files are different from ship/XBT ones as they can contain either one unique observation, one time series at a fixed point (one station) or all the research campaigns of a vessel.

Analysis

1564 (61%) of these platforms have an identified institution while 1021 (39%) do not. The 1564 identified bottle platforms belong to 48 different institutions.

In the same way, 1575 (61%) bottle platforms are also identified by a country (which means that 1010 (39%) are not associated with a country) which represent altogether 31 different countries. The distribution is not relevant, as previously said, because there are 3 different bottle platform file types.

All the platforms have a platform code and 81% of them also have a platform name, although sometimes it is simply a number. Some of the platforms are also identified by a WMO, this is the case for 18% of them (464 platforms) or/and by an ICES code, again for 18% of them (473 platforms).

303 platforms (12%) are referenced by a project code which is either ILICO (France's multi-agency Research Infrastructure for coastal ocean observation), Fr-OOS (French Ocean Observing System) or GOSUD (Global Ocean Surface Underway Data). Bottle platforms are not part of JERICO.

Physical parameters measured are temperature (87%) and salinity (78%), and the biogeochemical parameters are oxygen (65%), the nutrients: nitrate (58%), phosphate (67%) and silicate (50%), chlorophyll-a (43%) and the carbonate system (35%).

The two oldest measurements were made in 1860 by ships of unknown institutions and countries and there are 1% (29) of the ship/bottle platforms active in 2024 and at the very beginning of 2025 (operational) just before the upload of the coastal data for this study.

Tide gauge platforms (TG)

Tide gauges are platforms dedicated to the continuous observation of sea level. Sea level observation is coordinated in GLOSS (Global Sea Level Observing System), a component of the GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System), with the objective of monitoring long-term trends in sea level and general ocean circulation.

Inventory and status

The Copernicus Marine Service provides access to data from 683 tide gauges. As historical platforms, tide gauges are located along the majority of European coastlines.

Figure 8. Tide gauge stations in the Copernicus Marine Service.

Analysis

A total of 25 countries are responsible for the operation of tide gauge stations, with 54% of these stations being operated by five European countries. France and the Netherlands are responsible for the operation of 26% of the platforms. In those countries, 59 institutions are involved.

Figure 9. Percentage of tide gauges per country.

As land structures, they are not associated with a WMO platform code. 23.4% (160) of the platforms are referring to a project, and the majority of them are tagged as JERICO platforms (22.5% - 154 platforms).

For tide gauges, the main measured parameter is sea level. However, at 95 stations (14%), temperature measurements are also collected. Time series can extend over a period of more than a century, with six stations having recorded observations prior to 1900. The majority of tide gauges are currently operational, with collected data for 541 stations (79%) since the beginning of 2025.

Drifting buoy platforms (DB)

A drifting buoy is an oceanographic platform floating on the surface of the ocean. It is launched from a boat and drifts across the ocean with the currents.

Inventory and status

Figure 10. Buoys launched in the coastal European area in the Copernicus Marine Service.

The Copernicus Marine Service counts 2577 buoys launched in the coastal European area. Some of them remain in coastal areas while others drift in the open ocean during their lives. Each dot corresponds to a buoy for which the data (time series of the drift) is gathered in a file.

Analysis

59% out of these 2577 buoys have an identified institution divided between 16 different organisations.

1540 (60%) buoys have a known country for a total of 10 different countries, with a distribution of buoys as follows (and in Figure 11):

- India, Netherlands: 1
- Canada: 3
- UK: 5
- Belgium: 11
- Spain: 14
- Germany: 16
- Italy: 96

- France: 678
- USA: 715

Figure 11. Percentage of buoys per country (for 60% out of the total number of buoys).

All the buoys have a platform code and most of them (2567 out of 2577) have a platform name, while 81% have a WMO code— which makes sense as they are often part of international programmes. Nevertheless, 27% (684) of the platforms have an associated project/programme which is either Fr-OOS (French Ocean Observing System), IABP (International Arctic Buoy Programme) or Trusted (Toward fiducial Reference measurements of Sea-surface Temperature by European Drifters) and as expected there is no JERICO reference as the buoys are not part of the RI in the making.

More than a quarter of the drifting buoys (27%, 696 buoys) allow for the calculation of the surface current speed. Otherwise, most of the buoys (2549, 99%) measure temperature while a very few measure salinity (1%, 29) or waves (1%, 18). Four buoys have only meteorological parameters.

Buoys drift on the surface or subsurface of the ocean, however 545 (21%) of them also provide measurements in the water column from a few meters to a maximum of 400 m deep.

The period of measurements (first measurement, last one) is lower or equal to six months for 60% of the buoys, 15% last between six months and one year, and 21% more than one year. The first 10 buoys integrated in Copernicus were launched in 1991 (not identified by a WMO, institution or country) and during 2024 and the very beginning of 2025, there were 118 active buoys (5%).

Profiling floats (PF)

Profiling floats are submersible robots equipped with physical and/or biogeochemical sensors. These devices are used as autonomous platforms for the purpose of sampling essential ocean and biological variables, with a depth range extending from 2000 m depth to the surface. The deployment of these profiling floats is primarily undertaken within the framework of the Argo programme. In coastal seas, profiling float behavior is adapted with a higher sampling frequency (to sample a shallow water column) and with a shallow drifting depth or bottom landing periods between two profiles.

Inventory and status

In coastal regions, data from 853 profiling floats can be found in the Copernicus Marine Service. The majority of the profiling floats are associated with the Argo programme and identified as standard Argo profiles in deep water but close to the coast (e.g. narrow shelf). However, certain platforms, for example in the North Sea or over the continental shelf in the Bay of Biscay, are profiling floats adapted for shallow waters.

Figure 12. Profiling floats in coastal regions in the Copernicus Marine Service.

Analysis

Profiling floats are deployed by 19 countries and 39 institutions. In European waters, the main contributors are:

- France: 277
- Italy: 186
- USA: 98
- Spain: 67

with more than 50 platforms each. Then:

- Germany: 48
- Finland: 40
- Greece: 35
- United Kingdom: 25
- Europe: 25 (ERIC Euro-Argo)
- Bulgaria: 20
- Poland: 11

And finally, Ireland (7), Turkey (6), Denmark (3), China (2), Romania (1), Netherlands (1), Morocco (1), and Lebanon (1) each deployed less than 10 platforms.

Profiling floats are all identified with a WMO platform code, which is the way the Argo programme was designed. However, no project is attributed to any float.

The first available data are from 1998, and in 2025, 116 (14%) platforms remain operational.

FerryBox platforms (FB)

FerryBox platforms have been designed as cost-effective tools for the collection of underway (en route) ocean data. Sensors installed on ferries facilitate the measurement of a wide range of marine parameters, including sea temperature and salinity. In addition, depending on the configuration of the FerryBox, other essential oceanic and biological variables may also be measured. FerryBox measurements are surface high-frequency measurements that allow for a fine spatial resolution.

Inventory and status

In the Copernicus databases, 73 platforms are providing observations. Equipped ferries are predominantly located in northern Europe. Less FerryBox data are available in the Mediterranean and the Black seas.

Figure 13. Initial position of Ferrybox lines in the Copernicus Marine Service

Analysis

All platforms are identified by an institution and a country except for five of them. 17 institutions are and have been involved in the deployment of FerryBox. These institutions are from 10 countries. However, a substantial majority of platforms (52, 71%) are operated by two institutions (STENA and SMHI) from Sweden.

As of 2025 (January only, before the dataset was collected for this study), Ferrybox data were mostly received from platforms located in Sweden, with a total of 35 active platforms recorded. Additionally,

two platforms from Norway and one from Poland were included, bringing the total number of active platforms to 38, representing 52% of the total. Presently, the sole location for FerryBox sampling is in the North Sea.

The initial FerryBox data to be found in the Copernicus Marine Service originates from the "Pride of Bilbao", a ferry operated by the United Kingdom, and dates back to 2005. Subsequently, in 2008, Sweden initiated the deployment of FerryBox on ferries.

WMO platform codes are assigned to 11 FerryBoxes (15%).

With regard to the projects, it is notable that 10 FerryBoxes have been tagged with the GOSUD (Global Ocean Surface Underway Data) programme. No specific platform has been identified as being associated with the JERICO projects.

Measured parameters are temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen concentration, fluorescence, turbidity, and colored dissolved organic matter. Sea temperature is the root parameter measured with all FerryBoxes.

Glider platforms (GL)

A glider is an autonomous platform that moves in the ocean in the horizontal plane and from the surface to a maximum of 1000 m deep in a sawtooth pattern. It is remotely controlled and can be operated for months and over thousands of kilometers before being fished out. The glider is equipped with sensors that allow for the measurements of physical and biogeochemical parameters in the water column (and then along transects).

Inventory and status

Figure 14. Initial position of gliders in the Copernicus Marine Service

There are 113 glider (GL) platforms within the Copernicus Marine Service having a first launch in coastal European waters. Gliders make measurements with varying longitude, latitude, depth and time. The gaps within the files mean a new launch with longitude and latitude as well as time, that can vary a lot from previous data. As a result, it is possible that the files contain observations far from European coasts, depending on the following deployments.

Analysis

All the 113 glider platforms are identified by an institution and a country. The platforms come from 28 institutions and 14 countries. It is mainly four countries: Italy, Spain, UK, France that have launched most of the gliders (84%); the detailed distribution is as below:

- UK, France: 31
- Spain: 23
- Italy: 11
- Germany: 4
- Cyprus, Norway: 3
- Belgium, Estonia, Greece, Finland, Ireland, Israel, USA: 1

All platforms are identified by a platform code and by a platform name (except for one of them). They also have a WMO (except for four of them) The only project referenced is again the Fr-OOS

(French Ocean Observing System) for the 31 French gliders. There is no reference of JERICO as anticipated.

All the platforms measure temperature and salinity, and 62% of them contain other parameters, broken down as follows: chlorophyll-a (58%), oxygen (34%) and nitrate (4%).

Gliders are a relatively new platform type with first measurements made in 2004-2005 (at least the ones integrated in the Copernicus Marine Service) by Germany and France. The period of measurement (first measurement, last one) varies from a few days or months to several years. 32 gliders (28%) were active in 2024 or at the very beginning of 2025 before the files were downloaded from Copernicus.

HF Radars (HF)

High-Frequency Radars (HF Radars) are coastal observing systems that allow for remote observations of surface currents (typically over the first meter depth) and surface wave measurements (not yet in the Copernicus Marine Service) from the coast. It provides continuous real time observations centralised in the European HFR node (implemented in 2018 - <https://www.hfrnode.eu/>) prior to dissemination of standardized Near Real Time (NRT) and Delayed-Mode (DM) HFR radial and total current data to the Copernicus Marine Service (through In Situ TAC), EMODnet Physics, and SeaDatamet.

Inventory and status

Within the Copernicus Marine Service, there are 59 HF Radar platforms providing observations from European coastal seas. All platforms are organised in 19 HF Radar networks, providing currents at each platform, but also total currents combining all platforms from each network.

Figure 15. HF Radar platforms (preliminary map - some positions need to be corrected) in the Copernicus Marine Service.

Analysis

Institutions are all identified and correspond to 19 different ones. Countries are not explicitly documented, but we find eight different countries, with two of them: Spain (28 platforms - 47% of HF Radars) and Italy (17 platforms - 29% of HF Radars) having most of the platforms operated. These platforms are distributed over countries as follows:

- Spain: 28
- Italy: 17
- Malta: 4
- Norway: 4
- Germany: 2
- Slovenia: 2
- France: 1
- United Kingdom: 1

They are all identified by a WMO platform code, with the exception of one platform.

56% (33) are referenced by a project code. 19% (11) are referring to a JERICO project (FP7 JERICO-NEXT or H2020 JERICO-S3).

93% of the HF radars remain active and provide data since the beginning of 2024. The first HF Radar measurements available on Copernicus were collected in Italy in 2013.

3. River data

Introduction

While river climatology and research quality data are linked in from the [Global Runoff Data Center](#) (GRDC), since 2018 and focusing on coastal areas and including only stations located near the river mouths, EMODnet Physics (in collaboration with +ATLANTIC CoLAB) operates the near real time river runoff product. The system collects data from the hydrologic station nearest to each river's coastal area, excluding stations influenced by tides. River outflow may be a direct outflow measurement or a derived value from river water level (according to a conversion law based on each station river section). Some stations also provide water temperature and water level records.

In contrast with ocean data, river data management differs drastically from country to country, hence river data is collected from each data provider several times per day and is normalized, harmonized, and made available in near-real time through a dedicated ERDDAP server with full metadata description. During the FOCCUS project, a river station repository was added to the project ZENODO (Campuzano, F. (2025). River data [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15650422>).

Inventory and status

Currently, the EMODnet River Node collects information from over 1,000 stations, supplied by 40 national and regional water administrations across 23 countries on three continents: Europe, North America and South America (Figure 16). The service, as can be appreciated in the Figure, focuses mainly on the European coast with monitoring stations covering most parts of the European Atlantic

façade, the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. In the Mediterranean Sea, some areas are still uncovered and there is a clear unbalance between the European and the African coasts.

Figure 16. Current coverage of near-real-time river stations.

Currently EMODnet Physics is assigning a unique id to river stations, using the following naming convention for daily NetCDF files. Each file contains the river variables observed during that day and the number of values is not regular among stations since providers might publish their data with different regularity (from 10-minute observation to a daily average).

Analysis

In European waters, the main contributors are:

- United Kingdom: 163 stations
- Spain: 107 stations
- France: 107 stations
- Norway: 97 stations
- Sweden: 62 stations

with more than 50 platforms. Then:

- Finland: 42 stations

- Ireland: 35 stations
- Portugal: 17 stations
- Italy: 17 stations
- Poland: 16 stations
- Estonia: 13 stations
- Netherlands: 10 stations
- Denmark: 9 stations
- Belgium: 7 stations
- Greece: 5 stations
- Germany: 5 stations
- Slovenia: 4 stations
- Bulgaria: 1 station

Slovenian (Adriatic Sea) and Bulgarian (Black Sea) stations were added during the FOCCUS project to support these application areas.

Outside Europe, there are stations from Canada (133 stations), USA (20 stations), Peru (18 stations) and Argentina (3 stations) and Brazil in collaboration with the WMO Hydrological Observing System. Figure 17 shows the relative importance of each provider except Brazil in the EMODnet river node.

Figure 17. Percentage of near-real time river stations per country.

The number of providers and rivers change from country to country. While most countries provide a centralised distribution service, others may have a quite fragmented distribution service i.e. Spain with 12 providers lead the number of different providers to the service. Each station data is then enriched with metadata indicating EDMO code (institution owner), GRDC association and variables identification according to NERC dictionaries. To consume data operationally, the user may directly connect to the ERDDAP data collection (<https://erddap.colabatlantic.com/erddap/files/>).

A resulting example is shown in Figure 19 with near real time (NRT) river flow and water level for the Almourol Station in the Tagus River near its mouth. Original data are collected from the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA), standardised and enriched with metadata that can be checked in this url: https://erddap.colabatlantic.com/erddap/info/RS_PT_Tagus_Almourol/index.html.

Figure 19. river data of the Almourol Station in the Tagus River from the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA).

4. Conclusion

The coastal data within the Copernicus Marine Service already have a robust level of information (metadata) and a well-defined organisation of datasets by platform type, which is clear and consistently applied. For the purposes of this study and to enable a more detailed analysis and identify potential improvements, the EU dataset of coastal dataset (following the CoastPredict definition) has been divided into the 10 main platform types that Copernicus integrates, namely ship/XBT, ship/CTD, ship/bottle, mooring, tide gauge, buoy, profiler float, FerryBox, glider and HF radar.

The first results of this study shows the important number (10479) of coastal European platforms available in the Copernicus Marine Service, 13% of the total number of platforms within Copernicus. These include both stationary and moving platforms. Among stationary platforms, there are 858 fixed buoys/moorings, 683 tide gauges and 59 HF radars. Moving platforms are also well represented, including 597 Ship/XBT, 2,063 Ship/CTD, 2,585 Ship/bottle, 2,577 drifting buoys, 853 profiling floats, 73 FerryBox and 113 gliders.

Feedback from data providers, data managers and users could allow for increasing this number, however the added value of this study is to make a status of the EU coastal dataset in the Copernicus Marine Service with the objective to enhance the data management and traceability of the data.

The study has highlighted a few errors that can be easily corrected by the In Situ TAC (in situ component of the Copernicus Marine Service). For most of the platform types (instruments on board vessels, moorings, FerryBox, HF radar), the cross check of platform code (including WMO or ICES when relevant), institutions and countries might enhance any of these metadata. For the vessels, the name of the ship (platform name) could also be of some help to determine the institution and the country when missing.

There are very few programmes/projects identified yet and it is not clear how to do it (overview, granularity) although it will make sense to include RI (such as ARGO, the future JERICO and international programmes such as GLOSS or DBCP). However, this study (to be reflected in the last deliverable) is the opportunity to set rules with data managers and start enhancing the in situ data files as this will clearly improve the data traceability (strong provider request).

A tricky point, known from the data managers, is the many different ways to name an institution (with or without acronyms, head office versus laboratory) that might be upgraded by a hierarchy between parent and child institution. There is already some discussion in the Copernicus In Situ TAC on what to do and how to proceed (including the BODC and SDN vocabulary) that will benefit this study.

Rivers bridge the gap between land and ocean, influencing circulation patterns, biotic diversity and essential processes such as eutrophication. For the first time, the coastal and ocean communities have access to a service that provides international standardized near-real time river data across Europe. The continuous development of the EMODnet Physics River Node, with ongoing support from the LandSeaLot project, reflects a crucial step towards comprehensive coastal and ocean management. Within the FOCCUS project, the aim is on cataloguing these datasets and identifying metadata gaps: value outside of rating curve, observed negative values, etc. as well as metadata needed to comply with the Copernicus Marine Service so the EMODnet River Node can be also distributed through this European data integrator.